

ALIGNING THE EXCELLENCE OF ACCOUNTING SOFTWARE APPLICATION WITH A REVIEW OF THE COLLEGE CURRICULUM

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Abstract

Accounting software always accompanies the company's business throughout life and adapts to changes in transactions and technology in business. Without reliable and adequate accounting software, a company will have difficulty making accurate and quick respond decisions faced with the volume of transactions in business competition.

This paper discusses how to align the advantages of accounting software applications in improving business performance with the latest developments in information technology and how higher education curricula provide subject matter to equip competent graduates with ability to refer to the competencies required by standard accounting professional organizations. In general, there are 3 things discussed in this paper namely firstly the development of accounting practices in accordance with changes in information technology, secondly revealing the facts of research results that accounting software can improve business performance and third how universities review the accounting software curriculum that students learn so they can use their practical abilities to operate books in accordance with accounting principles so as to support quality decisions for the company.

This research is a literature study taken from various studies on accounting software and supporting curriculum. The purpose of this research is as a critical analysis to determine the road map of teaching accounting software application teaching curriculum, examples of applied problems that are worth studying by students to improve their ability to solve problems in the world of work in the field of bookkeeping. With this research, it is expected that there is good synergy from professional organizations with higher education in creating accounting software learning methods and materials in facing the challenges of changing business and information technology in the future.

Keywords: *alignment, accounting software, curriculum review, information technology*

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. The Evolution of Technology for the Accounting Profession

Every accountant knows that accounting is the language of business. Through all the changes, accounting technology has always played a role in making the accountant's job a little easier. Technological advances have increased the ability of accountants to interpret data efficiently and effectively and analyze statistical data. The accounting industry now speaks a brand new business language. The evolution of accounting technology has been extraordinary with strong growth potential for the future. Company productivity has created career stability and opportunities in this successful professional accountant industry. Business owners start looking for professional accountants for technology advice. Accountants become trusted IT staff and advisors. By using a computer an accountant can now do statistical accounting or forecasting analysis with greater efficiency.

Accountants are encouraged to acquire new skills because of the advances in information technology that have been made in the accounting industry. Today's accounting professionals can use the internet to carry out major business processes in a company. Electronic business (e-business) allows companies to coordinate activities for internal management and combine client relations with the use of digital networks. Information can come from several different systems using the Web interface. They can display things like e-mail, internal documents such as the Code of Ethics, and search tools. This is a good communication tool in an organization. Clients not only need to have an advanced financial process, but accountants themselves need software programs that track client accounting information with increased efficiency. Accountants work with system programmers to develop digital processes that will manage the history of their clients and all their documents. When client data is entered into a computer program, the processing cycle provides computer instructions on how to process client data. Not only does an accountant need to have extensive accounting knowledge and a strong ability to apply accounting principles, government regulations and interpret tax laws; they must also have strong skills in information technology, to be able to combine accounting with information systems. [1]

The addition of the use of information technology has increased the existence of computer crimes such as; identity theft, e-mail phishing, computer hacking, software piracy, the intentional spread of computer viruses, stealing computer files and data, e-commerce sales and list fraud. The job market is open for CPAs who meet the AICPA qualifications to become Certified in Financial Forensics (CFF) for a career in fraud prevention. Also the Association of Certified Fraud Examiners offers Certified Fraud Assessors (CFE) credentials. Many doors have been opened for CPA professionals who are experts in this system. Because information technology takes a large part in running a successful organization, IT departments need to be managed. This manager needs to oversee that information technology supports the organization's strategy and objectives. Organizational IT systems must be ahead of competition, they must be financially responsible to the organization, they must be secure with a backup plan for failure and they must adhere to effective controls. [1]

To go further, cloud computing is becoming popular nowadays. This is called cloud computing because its name represents the symbol of the cloud used in a flow chart, representing the Internet.

This is a service provided via the internet to store data permanently and use business applications through a remote server. Software as a service (SaaS) is a web-based service. Data is stored permanently in large data centers that are shared by many other users. Twenty first-century accountants have strategic software applications to prepare for the future; such as an enterprise resource planning (ERP) system. This is a software program that integrates various departments in an organization into the same system. ERP improves business performance because management can obtain a complete picture of how business performance is at certain times which can help make key business decisions. Another strategic software application is the Supply Chain Management (SCM) system. This helps businesses manage relationships with their suppliers. [1]

Transition from desktop to cloud The move to "cloud computing" continues to increase in the accounting world. Doing calculations in the cloud means that everyone in the organization can access the same information and the same set of applications simultaneously. This involves major changes in the way organizations handle data. When accounting moves online, it is not in its own place - once you have online accounting, accounting naturally wants to be linked to other people, such as payroll, customer relationship management, your website, and your business application path. When accounting is locked in a desktop application, only a few people use it in the back office. Online accounting is multi-user, has different user roles that allow front-office staff to enter, and links to all other business systems. Cloud-based or hosted applications are a win-win for clients and vendors in terms of costs and revenues. [2]

On the client side, the user has a minimal initial cost or capital outlay, and a fairly fixed monthly fee. Unlike licensed in-house products, all support and upgrade costs for cloud computing are included, and clients don't have to worry about upgrades or backups. New features and functionality are automatically included in the software, so users know they always have the latest and best products. On the vendor side of the transaction is a fairly reliable income stream. There is no guarantee that the customer will be with the vendor forever, but assuming that the vendor provides a high level of service, they have a good opportunity to retain many clients on an ongoing basis. Another significant change in the world of accounting is the impact of generation Y. This generation has evolved with technology and is accustomed to its rapid changes using laptops, tablets and smart phones, and is connected all the time. To meet this need, accounting solutions must be integrated with tablet computers, smart phones, and other mobile devices. Therefore, cellular accessibility is now an integral and expected part of cloud computing packages. The online system also facilitates automated clearing house transactions between banks and electronic data exchange between suppliers and customers. [2]

1.2. Impact of Information Technology (IT) on modern accounting systems

The basic accounting tasks are as follows [3]

1. Check cash position: Because cash is the fuel for your business, you never want it to be nearly empty. Know how much you expect to receive and how much you expect to be paid over the coming weeks / months.
2. Record transactions: Record every transaction (collect customers, receive cash from customers, pay vendors) in the right account every day or every week, depending on volume Although

recording transactions manually or in Excel sheets is acceptable, it may be easier to using accounting software.

3. Documents and receipts: Keep a copy of all invoices sent, all cash receipts (cash, credit card checks and deposits) and all cash payments (cash, checks, credit card statements). Start vendor files, sorted alphabetically, for easy access. Many system accounting software lets you scan paper receipts and avoid physical files altogether.

4. Review unpaid bills from vendors: Every business must have an unpaid vendor folder. Write down each of your vendors which includes the billing date, the amount due, and the payment due date. If the vendor offers a discount for the initial payment, you might want to use it if you have cash.

5. Pay vendors, sign checks: Track your debt and provide funds to pay your suppliers on time to avoid late fees and maintain good relations with them. If you can extend the payment date to net 60 or net 90, everything is better. Whether you make payments online or send checks by post, keep a copy of invoices sent and received.

6. Prepare and send invoices: Be sure to enter payment terms. Most invoices will mature in 30 days, recorded as "Net 30" at the bottom of your invoice. Without due dates, you will experience more difficulties in predicting earnings for the month. To get paid faster, consider offering early payment incentives.

7. Review cash flow projections: Managing your cash flow is very important, especially in the first year of your business. Predicting how much cash you will need in the coming weeks / months will help you order enough money to pay bills, including your employees and suppliers. In addition, you can make informed business decisions about how to spend it.

New accountants must be familiar with software to help them carry out their accounting functions more effectively and efficiently. [4]

1. Accounting software contains basic accounting functions such as input, processing and output.

2. Income tax. Because taxation laws change frequently, it is very difficult to deal with them. Therefore, manual tax preparation becomes increasingly difficult and time consuming.

3. Audit. Information technology has also computerized the audit profession. The audit software package is currently available for auditors. For example, the trial balance software allows auditors to enter trial balances, handle all types of adjustment entries, and automatically calculate adjusted trial balances.

4. Word processing. Accountants use word processing software to prepare reports, billing, memos, and financial reports.

5. Graphics software. Graphics can be prepared using graphics software. Graphics can be printed on paper or displayed on slides, transparencies, and photos. Many auditors and managerial accountants use chart software to graph data in reports and financial statements.

6. Image processing. Creating, saving, and updating paper forms from documents takes time. In addition, it is very expensive to process and save documents.

7. Electronic data exchange (EDI). Electronic data exchange allows companies to communicate with each other electronically. Therefore, EDI allows companies to exchange documents electronically.

8. Electronic funds transfer (EFT). Companies can now connect to banks through EFT. This system allows companies to make payments and bill electronically. In this case, when the company wants to pay the debt to the supplier, they can do it through EFT. Furthermore, every time the company

makes a sale, the transaction is charged directly to the consumer's bank account and simultaneously credited to the company's account.

1.3. Desired financial reporting across the business spectrum [5]

Figure 1: Features Interested in Software Buyers [5]

Among the buyer samples, core accounting features such as ledgers, accounts payable and accounts receivable are almost universally requested. But things got interesting after that. Financial reporting, the top requested feature, includes things like balance sheets, cash flow statements, and income statements. By identifying and evaluating key performance metrics, this report offers a deeper insight into the financial well-being of businesses. Outdated accounting systems - and especially manual methods - cannot offer the same benefits. Other features that are frequently requested, invoicing and invoicing include the creation and distribution of invoices automatically, as well as the collection and processing of incoming client payments. The latest developments in AI and machine learning make routine processes almost instantaneous, freeing up resources for more complex tasks and analysis. Budgeting and accounting software forecasting functionality also uses AI, although in a different way: using historical data and trends to predict financial results and plan budgets. Emerging technology is a clear recurring theme here. Buyers are clearly aware of the benefits of recent technological advances, reflected in their desire to improve more sophisticated accounting solutions, driven by intelligence. [5]

Category of Accounting Software recommended for purchase [6]

1. Core accounting: Core accounting describes the group of software that manages company ledgers, accounts receivable and accounts payable, basic tax filing functions, and bank reconciliation. This is the minimum function of any accounting software that hopes to go beyond account tracking on paper or in a spreadsheet. This combination of features provides benefits for companies including consolidated reporting, easier tax filing, and deeper insight and control over company money. The core accounting system is available in cloud-connected and on-premise

versions. Online core accounting software connected to the cloud has the advantage of receiving real-time data from invoices, e-commerce, POS, and other online data such as bank statements.

2. Payroll: payroll software consists of the main categories of accounting software, and can be combined with general accounting tools or run as the best separate breed software. The team looking for the best payroll software should look for systems with connections to time and attendance software, automation for paid workers and working hours, and compliance with tax laws and regulations for company locations.

3. ERP: Enterprise resource planning software (ERP) is a feature-rich tool that combines many categories of accounting software from core accounting to inventory, e-commerce, supply chain management, and even business intelligence solutions. Depending on company requirements and software offerings, many companies can centralize all of their financial data in one complete ERP system. Because of its broad functionality, ERP software may not be right for every company. Many developing companies choose to stick with some of the best integrated breed applications rather than implementing ERP.

4. Billing and Billing: In theory it seems simple, billing and billing can be complicated and frustrating if you don't have the right tools. Billing and billing software manages complex accounting exercises carried out by many debt and receivables departments. The best billing and billing tools come in all levels of complexity, but most provide the ability to automate previous manual tasks and reduce manual entry errors. These tools come as part of a larger financial management software or can be found in the best independent choices. If researching the best breed billing and billing tools, look for connectivity to other accounting, sales, and offers to cash software that your company uses to stay organized.

5. Project Accounting: Project accounting software shortens complex project completion processes, between departments or between companies, especially those with sensitive resources and capital allocation. Providing time and expenditure tools, human and material resource management, and joint and project billing and project management task management features, project accounting tools bridge the gap between basic task-oriented project management tools and core accounting software.

1.4. Market Overview [7]

The Accounting Software Market is segmented based on Installation Type (On-premise, Cloud-based), End-User Scale (Entries & Micro Business, Small & Medium Enterprises, Companies), and Geography. The Accounting Software Market is valued at USD 12.01 billion in 2019 and is expected to reach USD 19.59 billion in 2025, with a CAGR of 8.5% over the forecast period 2020-2025. Over the past two decades, financial software and accounting market solutions have witnessed many changes. One of the biggest changes is offering cloud-based accounting software solutions.

1. The latest survey shows that, among companies planning to choose enterprise resource planning solutions, more than 50% are expected to choose cloud as a deployment model. Agility, lower initial costs, and faster deployment are the main benefits of cloud-based solutions.

2. Accounting software solutions are used to streamline the accounting process, to save time, and to ensure error-free transactions between companies and clients. This system is also designed to increase productivity, by archiving, automating and integrating human resource systems.

3. In addition, increased digital commerce and technological advancements, such as integration with other online applications, such as automatic bank feeds, automatic billing features, etc., and small and medium-sized businesses that collaborate with e-commerce players are expected to drive the accounting software market .

4. However, data security and privacy issues can hamper the growth of the accounting software market. [7]

Source: Arbitrue

Figure 2: Basic Motivation in Purchasing Accounting Software [7]

Current accounting software has some or all of the following features: [8]

1. Tight integration with Microsoft Office
2. Many products tend to point to the Outlook / Explorer interface
3. More accounting software products use technology such as .NET
4. There is a tighter integration of Workflow and Document Management
5. Improve Finance with Business Intelligence (Analytics)
6. Ability to pay invoices directly from accounting software
7. The ability for customers to pay your invoices directly from your invoice
8. More sophisticated supply chain, logistics, RFID, inventory and distribution issues are discussed in the product
9. The Human Resources Module is becoming more common
10. CRM integration increases
11. And, last but not least, pricing is easier because many products can now be purchased for a monthly fee or you can use Accounting by Wave for free. [8]

General Accounting	ERP Suite	Invoicing	Payroll
QuickBooks Desktop	Netsuite ERP	BillQuick	ADP Workforce Now
FreshBooks	Microsoft Dynamics	Zoho Desk	Patriot Software
Xero	Sage	BigTime	Dayforce
FinancialForce	SAP	Apptivo	Wagepoint
Sage Intacct	Oracle	Bill.com	Paychex Flex

Figure 3. World-class Accounting Software Supplier [8]

Good accounting software must have high functionality and its functions must be included in the software. Extensive system functions must include complete web empowerment and the ability to operate via the internet / intranet. It must have workflow capabilities, provide employee portals, provide alerts and meet IFRS accounting standards. It must be fully integrated or easily integrated with other relevant systems used by businesses. It must be connected seamlessly to other systems such as payroll, logistics, manufacturing and desktop software. Finally, it must have the capacity to grow with a business and be flexible enough to accommodate the changing needs of users or businesses. [8]

2. ACCOUNTING SOFTWARE AND BUSINESS PERFORMANCE

2.1. Impact of Accounting Software on Business Performance [9].

Conclusion Syahirah's research (2017) revealed that accounting software systems are very important and have great value for business, organizations and the economy. The flow of accurate and reliable information is very important for economic growth. Performance management plays a key role in increasing the overall value of an organization. Previous research has shown that adoption of accounting information systems does indeed improve company performance, profitability, and operating efficiency. This study shows that there is a strong relationship between the characteristics of accounting software and business performance, which means access to accurate accounting information, will lead to organizational effectiveness. Therefore, it can be concluded that accounting software has an impact on the business performance of companies in Malaysia. [9]

Figure 4. Conceptual Framework of Accounting Software on Business Performance [9]

2.2. Impact of accounting software for Business Performance [10].

An accounting software system is essential for producing quality accounting information in a timely manner and communicating that information to decision makers. Existing literature offers proof of the relationship between this Accounting Software System and business performance; Although it is important to highlight that in-depth study is needed to examine other factors that can influence this relationship. The dimensions of service quality (User-friendly, reliability, efficiency) have an impact on business performance by 66.4%. No effect on 33.6% on business performance.

Figure 5. Conceptual Framework of Accounting Software on Business Performance [10]

This study shows that there is a strong relationship between accounting software systems and business performance, which means access to accounting information, will lead to organizational effectiveness. Therefore, it can be concluded that the accounting information system has an impact on the business performance of Anuradhapura city.

2.3. Conformity of Accounting Systems in the Banking Sector [11]

According to the literature analysis, it can be stated that information technology influences the accounting process in several ways. First, accounting methods and business and industry

knowledge have improved to ensure the reliability and relevance of documents, reports and data. Second, accountants must better understand the flow of transactions and related control activities to ensure the validity and reliability of information. According to the results of the research the requirements for identification, analysis and verification of possible alternatives to solving the problem of the incompatibility of the accounting system with the business environment are found. According to the results, organizational managers can more easily recognize the possible direction of the correction, estimate the possibility of its application. The development aspects mentioned can be implemented with integration with information technology. The degree of influence of the business environment on the accounting system must be compatible with the degree of adaptation to the business environment and information technology can help ensure this process.

Figure 6. Impact of Information Technology on the Conformity of the Business Environment [11]

Information technology helps ensure compatibility between the accounting system and the business environment. When the accounting system does not provide information that is useful for the decision making process, information technology can be a tool for the conformity process. Scientific implications. The theoretical framework presented contributes to the accounting literature by analyzing the information technology that shapes and ensures the conformity process between the accounting system and the business environment in which the organization operates and also by introducing problems encountered in the suitability of the identification process.

3. INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY INTO ACCOUNTING AND FINANCE

3.1. Accounting and Information Technology Curriculum [12]

AICPA and the American Accounting Association (AAA) held an IT vision conference in November 1998. Participants represented cross-sections of US accounting and MIS academics. The main problem was overcome through a number of presentations and breakout sessions including the convergence of accounting and information systems. It seems that several universities are combining their accounting and IS departments into one department, replacing several accounting courses with IS courses, and taking various other innovative actions such as using ERP systems to integrate material into the business curriculum. It is difficult to ascertain whether this is a major trend. In programs where accounting and information systems areas are combined, there is an optional path that allows students to choose courses that are basically equivalent to IEG 11 or programs by doubling IT coverage. Placement statistics reported at the

conference show that significant premiums are paid to accounting students with extended IT courses compared to salaries paid to regular accounting graduates. Information technology requirements become stronger. For many institutions, the competitive curriculum has more IT courses than IEG 11 thought.

Most academic institutions cannot add additional IT courses without sacrificing existing elements of the current curriculum. It seems that the courses that are being cut to make room for IT courses are more technical accounting courses; However, I do not have hard data that can be used to assess the extent of this phenomenon. Assuming that it is widespread, it is reorienting the accounting curriculum in response to market forces. However, there is a significant shortage of trained academics with interests and skills in accounting and IT. As such, it is unclear how many institutions cannot adjust to meet market requirements and are relegated to secondary or service roles.

3.2. Information Technology in the Gerald Trites Accounting Curriculum [13]

For more than sixty years, accountants have tried to deal with the effects of computer technology on their profession. With the introduction of personal computers in the early 1980s, and the consequences of the evolution of networks and then the internet in the early 1990s, problems related to IT increased rapidly. The introduction of technology to society is one of the great revolutions of human history. The period of its existence is a relatively short time for the profession to absorb this revolution. To complicate matters, IT is not static, but rather changes very quickly, complicating the process of dealing with it. It should be no surprise that the profession finds itself in a state of chaos when it comes to understanding IT and its effects.

The purpose of discussing the Gerald curriculum is to consider the current state of the accounting curriculum in Canada and to make recommendations regarding its contents. Extensive references are made to the CICA Competency Map, as one of the guiding forces in shaping the curriculum, including some pros and cons analysis. The contents of the UFE are guided by the CA Competency Map, which is issued by the national Committee under the authority of the Provincial Institute. Many universities refer to Competency maps in determining the content of their accounting programs, especially where those programs are specifically targeted at CA Professionals. Competencies identified in the Competency Map are classified into six categories with "Information and Information Technology" being one of them. The Competency Map then establishes the level of competency needed for each specific competency in the map. For this purpose, he uses a three-level scale, from lowest to highest, Understanding, Detecting and Conducting.

Understanding Under normal circumstances, beginner level CAs at the level of understanding will be able to describe and explain:

1. the concept of a general business system;
2. transaction processing in possible business and accounting applications;
3. strategic considerations in the adoption and implementation of information systems;
4. information system elements and control techniques;
5. the importance of companies that have IT strategies; and

6. what are the main elements of such a strategy.

Under normal circumstances, a beginner-level CA at the level of detection ability will, in addition to the tasks mentioned above at the level of understanding, be able to assess a company's IT strategy by:

1. Identify, through CA's basic understanding of IT strategies, whether those strategies are needed;
2. Assess whether the existing strategy seems to be in line with the organization's current strategic objectives and whether it will require the adoption of a new computer system;
3. Identify, through CA's basic understanding of the main business processes, e.g., Purchases,
4. Accounts payable, payments and sales, accounts receivable, receipt and IT architecture (network, database), main systems, functional, and IT requirements of the entity;
5. Analyzing the material or ideas provided at an early stage;
6. Based on the work done, forming initial conclusions about the appropriate IT strategy; identify the benefits, implications or other possibilities that have been revealed by the preliminary evaluation; and identify the need for further work or analysis.

Under normal circumstances, entry-level CAs at the "perform" level, in addition to all the tasks recorded in understanding and detecting the above, can help an entity with its IT strategy by: [8]

1. provide advice on developing, or changing needed for, its information technology strategy to ensure it is aligned with the strategic objectives of the entity (the underlying knowledge includes knowing what are the various strategic approaches currently available); and
2. advise the entity about best practice solutions that are in line with the entity's strategic objectives.

3.3. Higher Education Curriculum in Greece [14]

This study presents graphs of relevant IT content from the Accounting and Finance curriculum offered at universities and TEI in Greece, which can provide useful insights about the strengths and weaknesses of higher accounting and financial education in Greece in relation to social and professional realities. The methodology that was followed was based on the analysis of curriculum content and IT-related syllabus modules from all departments of Accounting and Finance at the Greek University and TEI. This approach involves the following steps:

A. Information is taken from the websites of all Accounting and Finance departments. This information includes the module title, an outline and the number of modules needed to provide the degree. The wide gap in IT coverage across higher education in finance and accounting, which has been reported in relevant studies in other countries (eg UK, US, Canada), is also verified in the Greek context of both:

1. The nature of IT-related subjects including.

General Information Technology Modules and Information Systems. Almost all departments offer introductory IT modules, while there are a large number of departments (5) where database concepts are taught. In addition, application programming modules can also be found in 4 departments. The scope of the Information Systems concept involves teaching modules with titles such as Information Systems (3), Management Information Systems (3) and Accounting Information Systems (3). Finally, the introduction of e-business modules has begun to increase in recent years, because there are 6 departments offering between 1 and 3 relevant modules.

- b. Information Technology application module. 10 departments offer between 2 and 4 modules which involve the use of IT applications in accounting. The modules taught cover subjects such as financial accounting, fees and taxes, and auditing. On the other hand, 6 departments offer between 1 and 2 modules 2 which involve the use of IT applications in finance. This smaller scope of financial applications can be attributed to the fact that most TEI Accounting and Finance departments are the recent successors of the Accounting department
- c. The proportion of IT-related modules in the total number of modules included in the curriculum. This percentage ranges between 5% and 22.4% (9.2% on average) for General and IS IT modules and between 0% and 12.2% (7% on average) for IT application modules.

2. Problems relevant to the number and specialization of teaching staff

A significant number of IT modules and General Information (an average of 9.2% of the total modules included in the curriculum) and a careful syllabus examination show that the general objective is not to teach only the use of accounting and financial IT applications. (which on average comprise 7% of the curriculum) but also to make students understand the concepts behind technology and the broader context of their use so that they will be helped to use, evaluate, and control technology more effectively. Therefore students are provided in a way that is satisfying with the means to play the role of managers, designers or evaluators of information systems, as required by IFAC guidelines.

INSTITUTE	ACCOUNTING APPLICATIONS				FINANCE APPLICATIONS				TOTAL IT APPLICATIONS		TOTAL MODULES IN DEGREE		
	M	O	TOTAL	%	M	O	TOTAL	%	NUMBER	%	MANDATORY	OPTIONAL	REQUIRED
UNIVERSITIES													
Athens University of Economics and Business	0	0	0	0,0%	4	2	6	9,7%	6	9,7%	20	42	40
University of Macedonia	1	1	2	3,3%	1	1	2	3,3%	4	6,6%	26	35	46
TEIs													
TEI of Central Macedonia	3	0	3	7,0%	2	0	2	4,7%	5	11,6%	35	8	39
TEI of Crete	2	1	3	5,0%	0	0	0	0,0%	3	5,0%	26	34	39
TEI of Eastern Macedonia and Thrace	2	0	2	4,7%	0	0	0	0,0%	2	4,7%	35	8	39
TEI of Epirous	3	0	3	6,4%	0	0	0	0,0%	3	6,4%	35	12	39
TEI of Peloponnese	0	0	0	0,0%	0	0	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	35	10	40
TEI of Pireous	2	0	2	4,5%	0	0	0	0,0%	2	4,5%	33	11	40
TEI of Thessaloniki	0	2	2	4,1%	1	0	1	2,0%	3	6,1%	34	15	39
TEI of Thessaly	2	1	3	6,5%	2	0	2	4,3%	5	10,9%	38	8	42
TEI of Western Macedonia	1	1	2	3,3%	2	0	2	3,3%	4	6,7%	33	27	42
TEI of Western Greece	4	0	4	9,8%	1	0	1	2,4%	5	12,2%	37	4	39
AVERAGE	1,7	0,5	2,2	4,3%	1,1	0,3	1,3	2,5%	3,5	7,0%	32,3	17,8	40,3

Figure 7. Matrix of Information Technology Application Modules[14]

3.4. Integrate ERP (SAP) in the Accounting Curriculum

Approaches Used to Integrate ERP into the curriculum. There are three main themes that emerge from eleven studies. [15]

1. Develop learning materials for students. Studies show the complexity in developing learning activities. The instructor must develop relationships with the SAP University Alliance coordinator. Instructors must work together and coordinate with SAP and the university's IT department to ensure that the necessary technical and support infrastructure is available to support students and instructors. SAP through the University Alliance provides case studies and data to develop

activities directly. However, research shows that instructors develop their own activities and assessments. This may be because the case and data provided by SAP may not be technically or pedagogically appropriate. Learning outcomes for adopting SAP vary from a focus only on AIS to a broader focus for the company.

2. Training and instructor development. Most research reports the formation of faculty project teams to tackle technical and pedagogical problems to adopt SAP. Training for instructors is usually done through the SAP University Alliance. This training raises costs. Build activities for students including time-consuming grading assignments.

3. Integrate SAP into the curriculum. The instructor reported difficulties in establishing activities to integrate SAP into the curriculum. Integration of practical hands on activities with problematic theories. SAP's hands-on experience requires computer lab access for the students and curriculum committee involved.

A literature review reveals a number of benefits and limitations. The benefit of teaching using ERP, like SAP, is that the focus moves from the narrow AIS view to the view of the company's business processes. SAP Skills can provide graduates with valuable valuable skills. Activities and direct assessment are more likely to involve students in an active learning environment. The main concern is the instructor's skill currency. SAP is complicated and difficult for instructors to keep abreast of the skills they need to be able to teach SAP with confidence. Technical difficulties require time to complete and inconvenience IT, instructors, and student support.

3.5 Curriculum that enhances accounting programs. [16]

This study investigates whether students at Botho University who are registered for Hons BSc in the Accounting Program face accounting software challenges during their internship period. Accounting software for which students are expected to have knowledge includes: spreadsheet software, quick books and sage pastel accounting. Focus groups and face-to-face interviews were used to collect data from students enrolled in BSc Hons in Accounting at the Botho University Campuses in Gaborone, Maun and Francistown. This study focuses on students who are in the internship period. However, the majority of accounting students face the challenges of accounting software and agree that a computerized accounting software curriculum should be proposed and implemented at Botho University in the Department of Accounting and Finance. This is done to improve the Accounting Program and meet industry and trade expectations. The significance of this research is that, it will benefit many stakeholders including: educators in accounting, accounting students, universities, colleges and captains of industry. Implementing an inclusive curriculum that pays attention to practical skills will reduce training costs for prospective employers. In addition, graduates of the accounting program will be available so they may be able to: establish their own consulting firm and reduce the unemployment rate.

Figure 8. Sage Pastel Accounting Curriculum[16]

Some recommendations from the results of this study are:

1. Conduct workshops with students so they understand the importance and benefits of introducing the Computerized Accounting module at BSc Hons in the Accounting Program
2. Accounting programs must adopt concepts outside the classroom (the concept of hands-on or learning by doing)
3. Get approval from Botho University's Senior Management before applying the Computerized Accounting module. If the Computerized Accounting module is approved by Senior Management, submit it for accreditation with the Botswana Qualification Authority
4. Pilot the application of the Computerized Accounting module first before introducing it to many students
5. The assessment for this Computerized Accounting module must be practical
6. The teaching methodology of the Computerized Accounting module must be practical based and it is also important to involve accounting industries and companies during curriculum implementation
7. Coordinate and collaborate with Sage Pastel Vendors (Suppliers in South Africa) for detailed information
8. Training of faculty members with Certified Sage Pastor Facilitator
9. Next studies. Ask employers about the relevance or need to teach the Computerized Accounting module to Accounting students

10. Comparison of performance for students who have been exposed to the Computerized Accounting module and students who are not exposed to the Computerized Accounting module

The above results show that both focus group workshops and face-to-face interviews support the implementation of the Computerized Accounting Curriculum because it enhances the Accounting Program. This Computerized Accounting Module helps students master the skills needed during internships as well as in industry and commerce after completing the Accounting Program. Therefore, if this module is implemented correctly it can increase opportunities for employability and independence because graduates will have the skills and knowledge needed in the accounting environment. [16]

3.6. Relevant Information Technology Knowledge and Skills in New Zealand

This study has provided a holistic and comprehensive view of relevant IT knowledge and skills needed by NZ accounting graduates with empirical data support. It ranks IT topics in order of importance; detail the contents of important topics and propose a schedule for coverage of various topics in various programs in the accounting program. Findings from this study have enabled the development of models for the delivery of IT content in major accounting programs. It also shows, with evidence, that guidelines in IT education for accountants from several professional accounting bodies are impractical and difficult to follow. The following are the specific contributions of this research. [17]

Combined knowledge and understanding of accounting systems, together with practical knowledge and skills in the use of accounting software, is the second most important IT topic for accountants. Accounting software is used every day and accountants must have good knowledge not only in how to use accounting software packages but with a full understanding of the accounting system behind it. This requires a thorough knowledge of the accounting system or business. This finding is in accordance with the literature. Data collected from interviews indicate that the accounting system or business and accounting or business software are interrelated and must be taught in close contact with each other. Participants expressed a desire to study large-scale ERP systems in addition to small-scale accounting software packages that are often taught in TEI.

CA company participants want to learn about CA's corporate accounting software packages. Focus must be on the 'cycle' or components of a typical business system. This includes the revenue cycle (sales order processing, goods shipping, billing and collection), the purchase cycle (purchase order processing, receipt of goods and payments) and the general ledger cycle (account chart, journal entry, and report generation). It is better to use two accounting software packages to teach in the main accounting program. The first can be a popular entry level package, with the second in the medium to large ERP system range. Or, the second accounting software can be a special package for CA companies. However, teaching a second accounting package will incur additional costs and require additional time allocation in the accounting program. The second package choice is also

indirect because some participants prefer ERP while others want a company-specific accounting software CA [17].

4. CLOSING

Impact of the use of accounting software on the acquisition of student knowledge: An important change in accounting education is on the use of software to the acquisition of student knowledge about the accounting cycle, basic concepts in business, and accounting. This research aims to provide a better understanding of the appropriateness of the use of software to increase knowledge, and provide assistance in curriculum change design decisions. Very few investigations have been carried out before in this field. Three different groups of students are examined: those who complete accounting cases: (1) manually, using a traditional pencil and paper approach; (2) using software; and (3) first manually and then using software. This study investigates differences in knowledge acquisition between these three groups. The results showed that the group of students who first completed accounting cases manually and then completed the same cases using software experienced better knowledge acquisition. This shows that the best way for students to obtain concrete knowledge from the accounting cycle is to solve cases using both methods. Learning is strengthened when students use manual information systems and computer-based information systems. Some educators believe that the use of software causes students to learn less about the basics of accounting because the software works too much. The results presented in this paper support the importance of a pencil and paper approach coupled with accounting software; the two approaches together provide the best knowledge acquisition. In the current study, software integration in the case of accounting provided tangible learning benefits. [18]

The main objective of the study conducted by Wan et al (2016) is to provide a pedagogical discussion on the potentiality of the treatment of accounting software in teaching. Accounting software offers alternative pedagogies that are still categorized as relevant that support the ability of information and communication technology among students. The application of accounting software can motivate students to understand the real world of accounting work because if learning only through textbooks is sometimes found differences in the work of accounting tasks in the field of work involving information technology. Therefore, a teaching method in accounting software in the classroom can be used as a learning innovation that supports traditional teaching and learning accounting processes. [19]

5. FURTHER RESEARCH RECOMMENDATIONS

Future research is on student learning material with cloud computing methods and mobile-based transaction systems using android mobile gadget devices. Here we will review the impact of cloud computing on these two main components (physical software and equipment) with respect to the similarity of the impact on them in terms of the fact that: 1. Cloud computing allows individuals and companies to use physical software and equipment without the need to buy devices software

and install it on their computer. Also, there is no need to buy some equipment, such as a physical server, because cloud computing provides a server for company data stored on it that is presented by Infrastructure as a Service (IAAS). 2. No need to spend money on infrastructure, technology or software to buy materials and equipment that provides capital cost facilities. 3. The Cloud service provider is responsible for maintaining and managing hardware and software. 4. Regarding the software added only new computing software that is simple and easy to use. [20].

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